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Experiment on the performance of different machine learning algorithms for classification

PEMAC24

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Experiment on the performance of different machine learning algorithms for classification project, delivered in section 4. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the FAIR data section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Moritz Fischer will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The datasets employed in this project cover a diverse range of domains, each selected for its potential to contribute to the study of machine learning algorithms in classification tasks. Here is a summary of the datasets utilized:

1. **Membership Woes Dataset:** This dataset originates from a premium club known for its customized membership fees and exclusive facilities. In recent years, the club has observed a significant trend in membership cancellations. The dataset includes various attributes of members and their engagement with club services, providing a basis to predict potential cancellations.
2. **Zoo Dataset (UCI):** Comprising 17 Boolean-valued attributes, this simple yet effective dataset is sourced from the UCI Machine Learning Repository. The primary goal using this dataset is to classify animals into one of several categories based on their attributes, using the "type" attribute as the class identifier.
3. **Breast Cancer Dataset:** This critical dataset includes detailed characteristics of breast tumors, with the aim to distinguish between recurrence and non-recurrence of cancer events. The data is vital for developing predictive models that can significantly impact patient treatment plans.
4. **Loan Dataset:** Featuring data related to various characteristics of loan applications, this dataset is used to predict the scoring of a loan application. It

serves as an excellent resource for testing algorithms that handle financial analytics and risk assessment.

Each dataset is stored and managed under specific licensing agreements that respect both the use and distribution of the data. The Membership Woes Dataset and the Loan Dataset are proprietary and are made available under a CC-BY-NC-ND license which permits academic and non-commercial use while prohibiting the creation and distribution of derivatives. The Zoo Dataset and the Breast Cancer Dataset are publicly available and are also included under similar non-commercial restrictive terms to ensure compliance with data usage policies.

In terms of data handling, all datasets are maintained in their original format to preserve data integrity. They are accessed and manipulated using Python's robust libraries such as pandas, which facilitates data loading, manipulation, and analysis, ensuring that data workflows are efficient and reproducible.

The results and insights derived from these datasets are crucial for advancing the project's objectives, which focus on comparing the effectiveness of various machine learning classification algorithms. In terms of data generation, our project will primarily produce a JSON file containing all the collected metrics for the tested classification algorithms and mentioned datasets. Crucially, python scripts will be generated, housing all code, facilitating transparency and reproducibility.

Produced dataset (DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.11091262**):

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	experiment_performance_of_different_machine_learning_algorithms_for_classification_results.json	Structured text	JSON	1 MB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Zoo	DOI: 10.24432/C5R59V	CC-BY 4.0	no
R2	Membership Woes	URL: https://api.openml.org/d/44224	CC-BY 4.0	no

R3	Breast Cancer	URL: https://github.com/moritx/performance-experiment-machine-learning/tree/main/data	CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0	no
R4	Loan	URL: https://github.com/moritx/performance-experiment-machine-learning/tree/main/data	CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0	no

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

SOFTWARE IS ACCESSIBLE AND FINDABLE HERE:

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.11085222

REPOSITORY URL:

<https://github.com/moritx/performance-experiment-machine-learning>

The data for this project is sourced from various datasets including the Membership Woes Dataset, Zoo Dataset (UCI), Breast Cancer Dataset, and Loan Dataset. The last two datasets were originally provided by Professor Rudolf Mayer under a CC-BY-NC-ND License but not accessible for no participating students. For that reason the datasets were made available under the software repository with the same License. Each dataset is pre-existing and chosen specifically for its relevance to the classification challenges posed in the experiments. The data is utilized directly without additional transformation, ensuring the integrity and original structure of the datasets are maintained.

For data processing and experimentation, Python (minimum version 3.8) is employed, leveraging libraries specified in the **requirements.txt** file. The primary script, **experiments.py**, is executed within the **scripts/ex1** directory. This script conducts all classification experiments, handling data loading, processing, model application, and result compilation. Outputs are systematically printed on stdout and saved under the **results/** directory. Graphical outputs are stored in **plots/ex1/**.

The entire experimental setup, from data processing to output generation, is clearly documented, ensuring that the methodology is transparent and reproducible. The use of a virtual environment and Python ensures compatibility across systems and facilitates the replication of results at any stage. Additionally, the code and data handling procedures adhere strictly to licensing agreements: scripts are under MIT license promoting reuse, while the datasets are licensed under CC-BY-NC-ND, restricting non-commercial use and modifications.

The authors, Maximilian Süß, Katharina Schindegger, and Moritz Fischer, have ensured that the methodology not only supports the project's objectives but also enhances the reusability and reproducibility of the research. This structured approach to data analysis and experiment management is crucial for consistent and reliable outcomes in machine learning research projects.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Members of the scientific community, other students.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The data is structured in a object oriented format (JSON) which is easily readable and interoperable. For versioning, we consider a version control system like Git. This allows us to track changes, handle multiple versions of the data and code, and enables others to reproduce specific versions of your work.

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention. Version control is automated.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at dataset level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

A far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. All data is persisted in Zenodo, a persistent data store with a DOI assigned to our record and CC-BY License.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2024-04-29	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.11091262	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

ZENODO builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. ZENODO enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to: easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science. display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. easily access and reuse shared research results. <https://zenodo.org/>

No specific tool or software is required to access and reuse the data.

Data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol, see <https://zenodo.org/>.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

To guarantee interoperability and promote the exchange and reuse of data, the project will conform to established data and metadata standards, including JSON for both data storage and metadata documentation, and README files for detailing data descriptions. These formats are universally recognized across various fields and provide ease of access and interpretation.

Should the project employ specific ontologies or vocabularies, efforts will be made to map these to more widely recognized ontologies wherever possible. This approach will improve the clarity and interoperability of the data across different disciplines.

Additionally, the project's data will contain explicit references to other data sources, such as datasets from prior research or additional data created within the project. These references will be meticulously documented in the metadata associated with the datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided there are no data protection concerns.

Our scripts stored at a GitHub repository functions as comprehensive documentation, outlining each step of the analysis process. We ensure that the code includes thorough explanations and comments for clarity. Additionally, our README file offers a succinct overview of the project, describing the data used and the steps involved in the analysis.

The following data quality checks will be done: data entry validation.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to

provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

...

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with Moritz Fischer being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

No direct costs are to be expected for the archiving of data output and storage of code. Indirect costs could entail the effort the data manager will have to put in to maintain metadata and perform all tasks outlined in this DMP.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only
R4	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	Zenodo	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated. No ethical issues have been identified, all pre-existing data is fully anonymized and so are the result files of the classification procedure.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data. For reusability there are LICENCE files (MIT License) provided in any case for the software part used to carry out the experiments and for the produced data P1 (CC-BY 4.0). A copy of the MIT License and the CC-BY License will be provided in the repository which specifies how the data and code can be reused.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?